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Review Article

**COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES
IN DRUG DISCOVERY**¹T.M.Keerthi, ²S.Thasneem, ³M.Guruva Reddy, ⁴K.Venugopal¹Final year B.Pharmacy, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.³Professor and Head of the Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupati-517506.⁴Professor and Principal of Krishna Teja Pharmacy College, Tirupathi-517506.**Abstract:**

Drug discovery relies heavily on analytical techniques to ensure safety, efficacy, and patient outcomes. This review highlights the significance of various analytical techniques, including spectroscopy (Raman, Mass Spectroscopy, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance), chromatography (Thin Layer Chromatography, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography), and hyphenated techniques (LC-MS). Emerging techniques, such as High-Throughput Screening (HTPS) and High-Content Analysis (HCS), are also discussed. These methods facilitate the identification, optimization, and characterization of potential drugs, improving speed, accuracy, and comprehensive understanding of pharmacological mechanisms. The study explores the application of these techniques in various stages of drug Discovery, such as Lead optimization, lead identification, formulation development; Applications in structural elucidation, impurity identification, pharmacokinetics, and quality control are emphasized, Along with Emerging trends and advancements in analytical technology. The contributions of pioneering scientists, such as John Fenn, are acknowledged. This comprehensive overview underscores about the analytical technique and the critical role of analytical techniques in modern drug discovery and aims to facilitate efficient and effective drug discovery efforts

Keywords: analytical techniques, drug discovery, spectroscopy, chromatography, hyphenated techniques, high-throughput screening, high-content analysis.

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1.INTRODUCTION:

Analytical technique plays a major role in the field of drug discovery by facilitating the identification and optimization of potential drugs or drug molecule through many advances and emerging trends in the drug discovery mainly focusing on patient safety and efficacy and to increase the value of pharmaceutical aids. These methods are employed to decrease cost and timelines, improve speed, efficacy, accuracy, and comprehensive of pharmacological mechanism they also aid in the selection and optimization of candidates and improve candidate selection [1]. A wide variety of procedures are used in analytical techniques to evaluate the physical or chemical characteristics of substances, components or mixture. These methods range from simple once like weighing to intricate ones requiring specialist equipment [2]. These Methods range from simple ones like weighing to intricate ones requiring specialist equipment. [3].These Techniques can be broadly categorized into qualitative methods, which identify compounds and

quantitative method which measure concentration or amount. Common Techniques like:

- **Spectroscopy**
- **Chromatography**
- **Emerging techniques**
- **Hyphenated Techniques**

1.2 Drug discovery:

It is the process of finding and creating novel drugs to cure illness or medical conditions [5]. Drug discovery is an expensive and time consuming process that usually takes more than ten years from the point of discovery to regulatory approval. The price and arrival schedules differ greatly based on the particular medication and the intended ailments [6]. To find and maximize possible therapeutic candidates, a multidisciplinary strategy incorporating knowledge from biology, chemistry, pharmacology and medicine is used. Important stages:

- Identification of Target
- Hit Identification
- Optimization of lead
- Preclinical Testing
- Clinical Trails
- Regulatory approval

FIGURE: Drug Design process flow chart

Finding a disease and its target protein is the first step in the drug discovery process as the figure illustrates. The structure of the protein is established, and possible therapeutic candidates are found and refined through a number of phases, such as clinical trials and lead optimization

- Address unmet medical needs with practical solutions.
- Enhance the therapeutic regimen currently in place.
- Minimize the adverse consequences
- Enhance patient health outcomes [7].

Here is a well know scientist who made a big difference in how analytical methods are used in drug discovery; John Fenn, MD [1917-2010] he contributed in development of electro spray ionization mass spectrometry improved sensitivity and accuracy in pharmaceutical analysis, enabled analysis of large biomolecules and complex mixtures [8]. Drug discovery relies heavily on analytical technique to guarantee safety and efficacy [9]. There are some benefits of using analytical techniques in drug discovery; patient stability, medical quality, regulatory compliance, and quantification of impurities and quality control [10].

1. Spectroscopy:

Spectroscopy is the branch of science dealing with the study of interaction of electromagnetic radiation of electromagnetic radiation with matter, the most important consequences of such interaction of electromagnetic radiation with matter. The most important consequences of such interaction are that energy is absorbed or emitted by the matter in discrete amount called quanta. The absorption or emission process is known throughout the electromagnetic spectrum ranging from the gamma region. Spectroscopy is one of the main tools available for the study of atomic and molecular structure and is used in the analysis of a wide range of samples [11]. Drug discovery relies heavily on spectroscopy especially

- Structural elucidation of possible drug candidates
- Impurity identification and measurement
- Research on pharmacokinetics and drug metabolism
- Raw material authentication and quality control [12]

Types of spectroscopy which are used in drug discovery:

- Tandem Mass Spectroscopy

- Mass Spectroscopy
- Raman Spectroscopy
- Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
- UV Visible Spectroscopy
- Infrared Spectroscopy

2.1 Raman Spectroscopy

Raman spectroscopy has become increasingly important as an analytical technique because of the ability to interfere comprehensive fingerprint and the technological developments in Raman instrumentation. It has gained importance in scientist research and development sectors. To gather the Raman spectra, two key technologies have been used:

- Dispersive Raman spectroscopy
- Fourier transforms Raman spectroscopy [FTR] [13].
- Both types of Raman spectroscopy uses visible region radiation but dispersive Raman spectroscopy is used more because it produce strong signal, making it ideal minor component analysis

Time bound transient species like different hemoglobin derivative can be studied using Raman spectroscopy [14]. For measurement within bulk samples such as polymorphic content, transmission Raman spectroscopy can be used since it detects signals from deep within the sample [15].

2.2 Mass spectroscopy

Here only small numbers of the many biophysical approaches are available in the mass spectrometry (MS) for drug discovery [Benesch and Ruototo 2011] [16]. One illustration is the examination of biomolecules and their assembles through the use of MS- based proteomics techniques, which can offer method for protein quantification across the proteome, tracking of protein levels and characteristics of post- translational modifications and protein- protein interactions[Aebersold and Mann, 2016] [17]. The majority of enzyme targets are primarily suited to mass spectroscopy analysis because, in contrast to most conventional biochemical assessment of both substrate and product in these in vitro assays, provide that a mass shift a mass shift occurs

2.3 Nuclear Magnetic Resonance

For the past 40-50 years Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy has been critical tool for drug discovery and development. This is primarily because it can be used

To clarify the structures of lead medicines their synthesis intermediates, and the degradation products and contaminants of those drug molecules [18]. NMR

spectroscopy's primary use in drug research and development has traditionally been in the elucidation of small molecule structures. Assuming that the prediction calculation are accurate enough, certain NMR software, like Mnova5, also enables the user to predict the NMR spectrum of the molecule under study and provide an indication of the match between the predicted and experimental spectra, increasing confidence in the structure confirmation.

- NMR has excellent sensitivity and resolution
- NMR can analyze without destruction
- NMR has capacity to examine intricate mixes
- Fit for small molecules and biologics
- Study of protein-ligand interactions that is dynamic
- Information about structures of molecular interaction.

APPLICATIONS:

S.NO.	TECHNIQUE	TYPES	CATEGORY	EXAMPLES	REF
1.	Spectroscopy	Raman spectroscopy	Psychostimulant	Amphetamine and methamphetamine	[19]
2.	Spectroscopy	Raman spectroscopy	Histamine receptor	Ranitidine	[20]
3.	Spectroscopy	Raman spectroscopy	Sympathomimetic agents	Pseudoephedrine, ephedrine	[20]
4.	Spectroscopy	Raman spectroscopy	NSAID'S	Indomethacin	[21]
5.	Spectroscopy	Mass spectroscopy	Vaccine	Influenza, HIV	[22]
6.	Spectroscopy	Mass spectroscopy	Recombinant proteins	Insulin	[22]
7.	Spectroscopy	Mass spectroscopy	Cardiovascular drugs	Statins	[23]
8.	Spectroscopy	Mass spectroscopy	Immunology drugs	Rituximab	[23]
9.	Spectroscopy	NMR	Anti Cancer drugs	Tamoxifen	[24]
10.	Spectroscopy	NMR	Cardiovascular drugs	Losartan	[24]
11.	Spectroscopy	NMR	HIV protease Inhibitor	Indinavir	[25]
12.	Spectroscopy	NMR	Antibacterial	Linezolid	[25]

Table- 1

3. CHROMATOGRAPHY TECHNIQUES

Chromatography is a laboratory technique used to separate the components of a mixture and identify their presence by analyzing the colour and retention time of individual components. Chromatography is essential to the drug finding process. It is employed in the following process recognizing and isolating bioactive compounds from natural sources

- Separating and purifying drug candidates from complicated mixtures
- Evaluating the composition and characteristics of possible drugs
- Locating and measuring contaminants in drug ingredients [26].

3.1 Thin Layer Chromatography

Chromatographic constants were widely employed as indicators of the lipophilicity of the drugs under investigation, and the relationship between retention and molecular descriptors was examined. Which molecular characteristics affect the chromatographically determined lipophilicity is the most crucial knowledge in this kind of research. Multiple linear regression (MLR) and partial least squares regression (PLS) techniques are often used in the investigations [27]. In the past several years, a number of publications have been published that describe the relationship between TLC parameters and the lipophilicity of medications, xenobiotics, or significant chemicals used in industry, such as sunscreens [28], food preservatives [38], food colors [29], and artificial and natural sugars [30]. Because RP-TLC is the most widely used technique for assessing lipophilicity, the majority of

chromatographic parameters in TLC have been set for QSAR investigations

3.2 High Performance Liquid Chromatography

A key tool in the pharmaceutical business, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is essential to the identification and development of new drugs. Because of its strength, adaptability, and dependability, it can analyze a wide range of samples and yield insightful information on the concentration, purity, and chemical characteristics of possible medicinal substances. An improved version of column chromatography, or HPLC, is a method for

separating different chemicals from mixtures. Through high-pressure filtration of a mixture-filled column filled with tiny particles, HPLC is able to distinguish between distinct chemicals according to how they interact with the stationary phase (solvent) and the mobile phase (column material). More stationary phase interaction causes a compound to travel down the column more slowly and separate from other compounds that interact more. [30]HPLC appears to have a bright future in drug discovery, as new developments are anticipated to increase its effectiveness and adaptability even more. [31].

S. No	TECHNIQUES	TYPES	CATEGORY	EXAMPLES	REF
1.	Chromatography	Thin layer Chromatography	Opioid	Heroin	32
2.	Chromatography	Thin layer Chromatography	Stimulants	Amphetamine, MDMA.	32
3.	Chromatography	Thin layer Chromatography	Barbiturates	Phenobarbital, Secobarbital.	33
4.	Chromatography	HPLC	Hallucinogens	Psilocybin	34
5.	Chromatography	HPLC	Antidepressants	Sertraline, Imipramine	35
6.	Chromatography	HPLC	Antianxiety	Buspirone	35

Table-2

4. HYPHENATED TECHNIQUE

4.1 Lc-Ms Techniques

Fundamental advancements in Liquid chromatography-Mass spectroscopy (LC-MS) technology over the last few years have altered the medical analytical chemist's toolkit. New column technologies operating at higher flow rates, elevated temperatures, and ultra-high pressures, along with recent advancements in instrumentation, enable analytical scientists and medicinal chemists to obtain results with the highest information content from a sample more quickly [36]. The purification of individual compounds and libraries has been greatly impacted by developments in LC and MS application. In most cases, a medicinal chemist must devote 25–

50% of their lab time on the purification of chemicals. Purification laboratories have been established by numerous pharmaceutical corporations in an effort to create a technology platform that unifies data management, procedures, technologies, and approaches. Centralized purification labs with a high degree of automation and experimental expertise in analytical/medical chemistry are emerging as a potent weapon for maintaining achiral/chiral purification on a small and big scale at various throughput levels. LC with UV and/or MS-guided collection is the dominant method in this scenario, capable of producing hundreds of purified samples per week [37, 38]

S.NO	TECHNIQUES	TYPES	CATEGORY	EXAMPLES	REF
1.	Hyphenated Technique	LC-MS	Kinase Inhibitor	Gefitinib	37
2.	Hyphenated Technique	LC-MS	Anticancer	Daptomycin	37
3.	Hyphenated Technique	LC-MS	Anti Inflammatory	Celecoxib	37
4.	Hyphenated Technique	LC-MS	Antiviral agents	Oseltamivir	38

Table- 3

5. EMERGING TECHNIQUES

5.1 HighThrough Put Screening

High through put screening nowadays plays a major role in DD. Lately, industrial researchers and students working on their post-graduate and/or doctoral research projects have been increasingly drawn to High-Throughput Screening (HTS), a high-tech method for drug discovery. In essence, it involves screening and testing a vast array of biological effectors and modulators against predetermined targets. Protein and peptide libraries, combinatorial chemistry, genomics, and screening of combinatorial chemistry all benefit from the application of HTS ideas and techniques. By screening the vast compound libraries at a rate that may surpass a few thousand compounds every day or daily wee, this approach aims to expedite the drug discovery process.

5.2 High content analysis

HCS helps in drug discovery although the conceptual underpinnings of HCS technology are straightforward. The degree of sophistication attained in each of its three main components readouts, instrumentation or data collecting methods, and models has necessitated a protracted and ongoing developmental path. It is difficult to set a watershed moment for the invention of HCS technology, but the term “high content screening” was used for the first time in 1997 by K.A. Giuliano, D.L. Taylor and co-workers [39]. High-content screening (HCS) is a technique used in drug development and biological research to find compounds that modify a cell's phenotypic in a desirable way [40]. The fact that most first-in-class medications authorized by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) between 1999 and 2008 were found by phenotypic screening is evidence of the potential significance of HCS in drug discovery [42].

S.NO	TECHNIQUES	TYPES	CATEGORY	EXAMPLES	REF
1.	Emerging Technique	HTPS	Neurological Drugs	Rivastigmine, Atomoxetine	[41]
2.	Emerging Technique	HTPS	NSAID'S	Meloxicam	[41]
3.	Emerging Technique	HTPS	Oncology Drugs	Erlotinib	[41]
4.	Emerging Technique	HCS	Immunology Drugs	Rituximab	[42]
5.	Emerging Technique	HCS	Oncology Drugs	Lapatinib	[42]
6.	Emerging Technique	HCS	Cardiovascular Drugs	Losartan	[42]

Table -4

6. FUTURESCOPE: Prospects for the Future:

Future directions for analytical approaches as drug progress include:

- 1) Combining machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) for predictive analysis
- 2) Creation of cutting-edge chromatographic and spectroscopic techniques for the examination of complicated molecules.
- 3) The spread of cutting-edge technology like high-content analysis and high-throughput screening.
- 4) A stronger focus on automation, high-throughput capabilities, and downsizing.
- 5) Better cooperation between pharmacologist, medical chemist, and analytical scientists.

- 6) Looking into the possibilities of single-cell analysis and nanotechnology in drug discovery
- 7) Development in informatics and data analytics to analyze large, complicated data

7. CONCLUSION:

To sum up, our through investigation has shown how important analytical methods are to the drug discovery process, from target identification to clinical trials. The discipline has undergone a revolution thanks to the wide range of techniques, such as spectroscopy, chromatography hyphenated techniques and developing technologies. In the end these techniques have improved patient outcomes by greatly increasing the effectiveness, precision, and through understanding of pharmacological mechanism some of the study's main **conclusion includes:**

Among the principle findings of the study are the following analytical techniques facilitate identification and optimization of the lead compound. Chromatography and spectroscopy remain vital techniques in the hunt for novel medications. New technologies and hybrid approaches expedite the discovery process. Drug effectiveness, safety, and efficacy and quality control are ensured by analytical techniques

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